

APPROACHES TO SCHOOL SYSTEM AND DISCIPLINE: A GUIDE FOR BUILDING A FOUNDATION OF SUCCESS IN EDUCATIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICE

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Abstract:

The paper investigates the approaches to school system and discipline as a guide for building a foundation of success in educational leadership practice that focuses on discipline in school, discipline inside the classroom, management classroom learning, students' disruptive behavior, and teaching innovation. The research utilizes the descriptive quantitative research design because it explores research methods to describe the characteristics and variables in the phenomena of the educational system. Further, purposive sampling is employed because it challenges the application of selecting the sample size of the research process. The study composed One Hundred Fifty (150) participants only. Results indicate that discipline in school highlights the school system and discipline capacity to be the priority for progress and improvement of educational organization, discipline inside the classroom shows to provide conditions in the learning process and academic achievement based on teachers motivation and implementation in the school system and discipline, learning process, classroom management, process, and learning style. It provides emphasis in controlling behavior and disruption. This includes teaching demonstration and teaching innovation which is conducive for student engagement and learning characteristics in the classroom setting and diverse practice.

Keywords: *School system & discipline, educational leadership practice, classroom learning, classroom management, student disruptive behavior, and improved teaching innovation*

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INTRODUCTION

The perceived issues and gaps are identified in building a foundation of success of leadership in educational practices in addressing the problem and discipline. The educational system will not materialize effectively when the school leader is weak. Effective leader starts with a better leader who knows how to motivate people around. Good leaders know how to help and enlist school improvement and concerns. If educational leadership allows ambition or

personal relationship to decide and dictate the school system, it will result in distrust (Mallillin, & Laurel, 2022). Teamwork and lack of unity will result in chaos and confusion in the educational leadership and practice. The importance of educational leadership and role involves basic building of the school system. Strong leadership requires courage and decisiveness to facilitate a better atmosphere. It identifies the implication of leadership in educational practices during crises (Marshall, et al. 2020, pp. 30-37). Furthermore, approaches to the school system and discipline in educational leadership and practices are an art in handling the process. Educational leaders must have mastered the school system discipline and handling that will lead to effectiveness in navigating the role as educational leader on a daily basis (Mallillin, et al. 2024).

Approaches to school discipline provide impact in positive management for the staff and practice professionals. It establishes norms, rules, and policies in a positive way. It manages significant impact behavior control atmosphere and environment. Norms, policies, and regulations may be established consistently and enforced. The approach is really essential management leadership in the educational system and discipline (Mallillin, & Mallillin, 2019). It is a pattern to be followed to become effective in educational leadership practices. It conceptualizes discipline and approaches for the school system to pay attention in leading the school dynamics. It identifies an educational setting organization and discipline approach of exclusive intervention and positive behavior support to the educational leadership and practice (Mallillin, & Caday, n.d.). It identifies the approach in the educational discipline and system toward equitable success. School discipline explicates approach system integration and needs for a comprehensive response to positive development and equity orientation challenges and implementation (Gregory, et al. 2021, pp. 206-220). It increases impact on the approach to the school system and discipline that acts as a reform educational system. It examines the school system and discipline in educational leadership guidelines and conduct. It increases options in the school system and discipline to educational leadership in various processes and practices. It tends to increase the driven reform and transformation implication of the school system and discipline (Curran, & Finch, 2021, pp. 179-220).

Notably, the school leadership approaches and discipline collaborates and unites talents in the school system and setting for the forces and process of teachers. It helps in the improvement of the school system and leadership in education to produce a quality educational system. It ensures that educational leadership success and purpose in the academe improves the training and resources in the educational system. It proposes better collaboration with different leaders in terms of public policy, parents, students, teachers, and educators (Mallillin, et al. 2020, pp. 1-10). The perspective of educational leadership in academic and management control of quality education and form identifies the systematic management process and trends of the knowledge to improve the situation to the fullest. It evaluates the educational leadership roles and techniques in the school discipline and success. It reflects the notable leadership features, reflection, and characteristics of positive leadership in the education process and setting. It analyzes the support management practice of improved leadership. It concentrates to enhance the ability and quality of a leader in the educational system and effort in terms of practice, role, and policy making (Hammad, et al. 2022, pp. 6-25). Additionally, the role of a leader in the educational system has broadened the knowledge and school practice in a diverse culture and tradition to better function in the critical ability of the educational leader such as preferences, policies, and constituents. It explores the leadership practice in the educational system in terms of objectives in the school discipline and improved school environment. The school quality system management practice depends on a leader on how the process and implementation obtains the success of quality improvement practice and process to the

fullest. It evaluates the systematic role and analysis of the contribution of educational leadership in the school quality system. It analyzes the role of educational practices and leadership to understand the discipline dynamics and school system (McGinity, et al. 2022).

Moreover, the school discipline approach in building a foundation of success is centered on educational leadership and key principle qualities and characteristics. It creates academic vision and success for educational leadership in the entire organizational school system (Mallillin, 2021, pp 17-28). It provides a historical gap which is necessary to identify for both learners and lecturers in the various levels of academic achievement and performance in the school system. The role of educational leadership is to maintain and strive for a learning receptive environment to maintain safety for the school, lecturers, and learners. It structures a school healthy environment when proper management is done according to the policy of the educational system. It provides a comfortable and orderly classroom environment conducive for learning. Educational leadership is a responsibility and provides an impressive atmosphere when works are delegated properly with good leadership style function and responsibility. This emphasizes the educational leadership empowerment, acceptance, accountability, and responsibility in the school system. On the other hand, educational leadership explores instructional methods, curriculum content for improvement, success, and continuum. It borrows and adapts better management in a modern method as to techniques, tools, processes, and educational function and responsibility. The educational leadership role is to practice and explore school setting values, system, and discipline. It provides phenomena and examines the alternative contend of leadership practice in the school setting. It transitions the behavior and focuses on the individual traits of a school leader. It unfolds and provides deeper insights in the educational leadership for advanced quality of education to work and equips with innovative practice and knowledge as talents in the school system organization. It advances the leadership approach to the traditional process. It evaluates the protocols on the approach of leadership in the school system and setting. It demonstrates the role of educational leadership practice and draws attention to details and illustrative phenomena particularly on values of leadership and practice lens in the organization. It explores the details of educational leadership role and attention practice in the school discipline and setting system (Nelson, 2022, pp. 197-210). Absolutely, the role of educational leadership emphasizes on the leadership process in an optimistic approach. It identifies the positive school leadership approach in a cultural perspective system in the educational setting. It provides positive results to explore the prospective process of educational leadership role as to relationships, behaviors, skills, affection of leadership optimism, staff outcome, principles, policies, and ethics. It evaluates the credibility of optimistic leadership on innovative processes in the school system (Kouhsari, et al. 2022, pp. 1-21).

Subsequently, the practice and contribution of the leadership process in education provides an approach to school system and discipline as part of the foundation of individual teachers. Educational leadership manages the school system to act for the success and progress of the school organization. They provide both students and teachers better resources and educational systems to equip quality education. They contribute to teaching qualities, school discipline, and better management. Educational leaders provide constructive feedback to improve the system, environment, and school system. and improvement of curriculum. Educational leaders are becoming the best asset in the school organization. They are contributing to the success and failure of the school system and discipline. It involves promotion of school organization and development system to the fullest. It involves fostering the educational leadership contribution practice of the school system to provide quality education and potential success in the educational system

to mold future leaders from the students. It transforms and supports the educational organization and system. Educational transformation and quality systems have an effect on the progress and success of the school environment. It is a shared responsibility in the school organization. It contributes to a better educational practice and decision making school system as a foundation of educational leadership practice. It is a powerful tool in the leadership contribution school system and educational organization. It designs and implements for shaping the conduct, norms, expectation, school culture, and school policies. Educational leaders create and practice discipline in the school atmosphere and system to care and trust which is aligned with the educational vision and mission of the school system. It is necessary for the involvement and support for the educational leadership contribution, school organization and discipline (Yulianti, et al. 2022, pp. 98-113). Hence, the educational leadership contribution explores the issues, concepts, and knowledge relevant in weighing the school discipline and setting for possible solutions on the school premises for better conducive learning in obtaining the objectives of the educational system as one team in the organizational success. It addresses and provides educational leadership insights to explore school improvement and the school system. It is concerned with challenges, preparation, development, knowledge, and leadership learning (Harris, & Jones, 2021, pp. 41-53).

In contrast, effectiveness in the educational leadership and practices provide a well-being, climate, and performance for both students and teachers organizational systems. It is underneath that leaders vary from quality because it provides effectiveness to colleagues and impact for better student outcome. It promotes and builds effective leadership in the professional learning and organizational culture in the community. It provides educational leaders with reflection and experiences. Effectiveness of leadership needs to explore the premises through mainstreaming the capacity environment and challenges. It focuses on concepts and incorporates the clarity and consideration for efficient leader setting as a basis to help leaders and followers. Effective leadership is critical and controversial because nobody can please in leadership. This has been directed through educational leadership criticism and challenges on the mainstream knowledge and underpinned claims. It is a causal belief that effective leadership depends on concept analysis and focus. This analyzes epistemology to address effective leadership. It provides skills for an effectiveness system through structure process and ability of being a leader (Evans, 2022, pp. 325-348). An ever changing process of effective educational leadership is characterized by technical trends and emerging effects on the global skills of leadership. It relies on conducive premises in adaptive school leadership environment and culture. Educational leadership is effective when transformational leadership emphasizes the process as to good, better, and best. It is attributed to school leaders who have the intelligence and capacity in educational organization. It establishes the effectiveness of transformational leadership as determined and directed in the school system (Velarde, et al. 2022, pp. 163-184).

Statement of the Problem

1. What are the proper approaches to school system and discipline in building a foundation of success in leadership educational practices in the area of
 - 1.1 discipline in school,
 - 1.2 discipline inside the classroom,

- 1.3 management classroom learning,
 - 1.4 student disruptive behavior, and
 - 1.5 improved innovation process in teaching?
2. Is there a significant relationship on the proper approaches to school system and discipline in building a foundation of success and practice of educational leadership as observed by the participants?

Hypothesis

There is a significant relationship on the proper approaches to school system and discipline in building a foundation of success and practice of educational leadership as observed by the participants

Research Design

The descriptive quantitative design is used in the process of research. It is the best designed suited in the study to measure and quantify the variables under investigation. It describes the research method and characteristics of the research design and implementation. It focuses on answering the statement of the problem posited in the objectives of the study. It measures to quantify the school approach system in terms of discipline in school, discipline inside the classroom, management classroom learning, student disruptive behavior, and improved innovation process in teaching. It enhances to provide deeper reflection in the normative description of the researcher's analysis impressive process and attraction (Jenkins, et al., 2021).

Möttus, et al. (2020, pp. 1175-1201) explains that descriptive research approach is a predictive and explanatory approach in quantitative research design on various goals that are distinguished on shared and needed priorities in the analysis of data especially on the leadership function and responsibility of an educational setting practice.

Subjects of the Study

The participants of the study are the selected leaders in the various Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) in the private and public sectors. They are reliable and best respondents to provide the data for the study under investigation. The study is composed of One Hundred Fifty (150) participants only.

Sampling Techniques

Purposive Sampling is used in the research process. It is the application and challenges of the selection of population needed in the study. It considers the method in a novice manner, practice and expectation for the sampling of purposive situations. It provides a real understanding and process of population sample size. It provides details of practical decision and transparency in the sampling technique based on the criteria as defined by the researcher. This helps to get a reliable sampling technique and sample size in the research process. Hence, purposive technique sampling is subjective which balances cost saving and time, selective that meets the standard criteria where they are part of leadership in the educational organization, and judgmental using the criteria set in the study. All respondents

utilized in the study are educational leaders in the school system and discipline. It is non-probability sampling that relies on the idea in choosing participants as members of the population and surveys. It requires prior knowledge to be eligible as respondents in the survey platform. Purposive sampling access to subset convenience sampling. It establishes the sample population and sample size. It is essential in the option sampling to ensure and consider best design in the study (Denieffe, 2020).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. **On the proper approaches to school system and discipline in building a foundation of success in educational leadership and practices in the area of discipline in school, discipline inside the classroom, management classroom learning, student disruptive behavior, and improved innovation process in teaching**

Table 1

Proper Approaches to School System and Discipline on Educational Leadership Discipline and Practices in Terms of Discipline in School

Indicators	WM	I	R
1. It measures approaches to the discipline and achievement of student academic performance.	4.17	A	2.5
2. It views the school system and discipline to prepare students in their career path as part of the educational system.	4.13	A	4
3. It develops and sustains the spectrum of the system to thrive for the success and progress of students.	3.20	MA	6
4. It highlights the school system and discipline capacity to be the priority for progress and improvement of educational organization.	4.26	SA	1
5. It reforms the school system and discipline that focuses on school pressure and accountability to improve structure and policy achievement of the academe.	4.17	A	2.5
6. It uplifts the success and responsibility for the challenges and development outcome in educational settings and practices.	4.07	A	5
Average Weighted Mean	4.00	A	
Standard Deviation	0.397		

It indicates in table 1 that rank 1 is "It highlights the school system and discipline capacity to be the priority for progress and improvement of educational organization", with a weighted mean of 4.26 or Strongly Agree which means that there is a proper approach for school discipline among the respondents. Rank 2 is shared by the two indicators which are "It measures approaches to the discipline and achievement of student academic performance", and "It reforms the school system and discipline that focuses on school pressure and accountability to improve structure and policy achievement of the academe, with a weighted mean of 4.17 or Agree which means discipline must be framed on policy for the respondents to follow. Rank 3 is "It views the school system and discipline to prepare students in their career path as part of the educational system", with a weighted mean of 4.13 or Agree which means to measure the achievement of students for their career path. The least in rank is "It uplifts the success and responsibility for the challenges and development outcome in educational settings and practices", with a weighted mean of 3.20 or

Moderately Agree which means to uplift the success of individual respondents. The overall average weighted mean is 4.00 (SD=0.397) or Agree on proper approach to educational leadership and practices in the area of discipline in school.

Likewise, it is the key achievement for the school system and opportunity gaps. It underlies the solution in the setting of education for rewards and self-regulation to work hard from the school leader and personal responsibility. It promotes driven policies in the school system and discipline through competitive quality education. The school system and discipline provides policy and views on various levels of learning in the educational setting for the welfare of students. It prevails on performance measure paradigms and gives emphasis on academic performance and increase of students' school discipline and system (Mallillin, 2022).

Table 2

Proper Approaches to School System and Discipline on Educational Leadership and Practices in Terms of Discipline Inside the Classroom

Indicators	WM	I	R
1. It analyzes the success of leadership through monitoring the school discipline inside the classroom especially on the management of instruction and direction process inside the classroom.	3.11	MA	5
2. It provides a dimension apparent to the skills and achievement of students' learning process.	3.24	MA	2
3. Discipline in the classroom is a part of the policy school system for the vital success of students.	3.20	MA	3
4. It provides conditions in the learning process and academic achievement provided by the lecturers in motivating students to the fullest.	3.26	MA	1
5. It focuses on the practice and system in the educational output process.	3.16	MA	4
6. It allows information on effective models of teaching systematic learning quality for students' academic performance.	3.07	MA	6
Average Weighted Mean	3.17	MA	
Standard Deviation	0.073		

It indicates in table 2 that rank 1 is "It provides condition in the learning process and academic achievement provided by the lecturers in motivating students to the fullest", with a weighted mean of 3.26 or Moderately Agree which means there is a need for proper discipline in the classroom or better output among the respondents. Rank 2 is "It provides a dimension apparent to the skills and achievement of students' learning process", with a weighted mean of 3.24 or Moderately Agree which means to better enhance student achievement. Rank 3 is "Discipline in the classroom is a part of the policy school system for the vital success of students", with weighted mean of 3.20 or Moderately Agree which means guidelines in the school system is essential among the respondents. The least in rank is "It allows information on effective models of teaching systematic learning quality for students' academic performance", with a weighted mean of 3.07 or Moderately Agree which emphasizes that school discipline must be consistent for the learning process. The overall average weighted mean is 3.17 (SD=0.073) or Moderately Agree on the proper approaches to school system and discipline on educational leadership and practices in the area of discipline inside the classroom (Mallillin, 2023, pp. 1-17).

Table 3

Proper Approaches to School System and Discipline on Educational Leadership and Practices in Terms of Management Classroom Learning

Indicators	WM	I	R
1. It prepares students in building knowledge for academic success and performance in school.	4.01	A	5
2. It provides self-directed classroom management and learning programs in school setting and discipline as part of the goals in the educational organization.	3.36	MA	6
3. Classroom management and learning of students prepare them the skills and necessary adjustment for the challenges in efficient learning practice.	4.09	A	3.5
4. It is a learning out base approach where the framework of the learning is being given and students are given enough time to explore the learning style and process.	4.21	SA	1
5. It emphasizes the school system and self-directed learning practices and challenges in the school setting.	4.11	A	2
6. It analyses the skills necessary for learning, effective information and decision application practice in classroom management and learning.	4.09	A	3.5
Average Weighted Mean	3.98	A	
Standard Deviation	0.311		

It indicates in table 3 that rank 1 is “It is a learning out-based approach where the framework of the learning is being given and students are given enough time to explore the learning style and process”, with a weighted mean of 4.21 or Strongly Agree which means that classroom management must be fully emphasized in the educational leadership practices. Rank 2 is “It emphasizes the school system and self-directed learning practices and challenges in the school setting”, with a weighted mean of 4.11 or Agree which means that there must be a program according to the educational leadership and practices. Rank 3 is shared by the two indicators which are “Classroom management and learning of students prepare them the skills and necessary adjustment for the challenges in efficient learning practice”, and “It analyses the skills necessary for learning, effective information and decision application management classroom learning”, with a weighted mean of 4.09 or Agree which means classroom management in learning is a great challenge for the educational leaders to implement. The least in rank is “It provides self-directed classroom management and learning programs in school setting and discipline as part of the goals in the educational organization”, with a weighted mean of 3.36 or Moderately Agree which means classroom management will be the ultimate goal of the educational leadership. The overall average weighted mean is 3.98 (SD=0.311) or Agree on the proper approaches to school system and discipline on educational leadership and practices in the area of classroom management and learning.

Therefore, classroom management in learning requires creativity and practice during difficult moments management classroom learning. It involves complex issues in the classroom management and learning pedagogy and content knowledge. It prepares students on their role in the educational system for growth and change in all situations of learning. Classroom management and learning evolves in the school system and discipline for self-directed learning. It identifies the educational approaches in classroom management and learning to promote success (Mallillin, & Paraiso, 2022).

Table 4

Proper Approaches to School System and Discipline on Educational Leadership and Practices in Terms of Student Disruptive Behavior

Indicators	WM	I	R
1. It provides emphasis in addressing the critical behavior of students.	4.29	SA	1
2. There is policy in addressing the behavior of students in the school based on trauma, violence, and mental health.	3.31	MA	6
3. It ensures that professional teachers are uniquely trained to mobilize the disruptive behavior of students to engage issues of discipline.	3.93	A	5
4. Students are given orientation on the school system and discipline inside the classroom to provide rich understanding principles inside the classroom.	4.09	A	2.5
5. Behavior and attitude of students must be guarded considering their situation as adults to explore experiences in the discovery process of learning.	3.97	A	4
6. It prepares students information in advanced utilization of learning appropriately to their behavior and services.	4.09	A	2.5
Average Weighted Mean	3.95	A	
Standard Deviation	0.333		

It reveals in table 4 that rank 1 is "It provides emphasis in addressing the critical behavior of students", with a weighted mean of 4.29 or Strongly Agree which means disruptive behavior of students is focused on clear consistency in the learning process. Rank 2 is shared by the two indicators which are "Students are given orientation on the school system and discipline inside the classroom to provide rich understanding principles inside the classroom", and "It prepares students information in advanced utilization of learning appropriately to their behavior and services", with a weighted mean of 4.09 or Agree which means students are guided properly on their learning process and discipline. Rank 3 is "Behavior and attitude of students must be guarded considering their situation as adults to explore experiences in the discovery process of learning", with a weighted mean of 3.97 or Agree which means addressing the behaviors of students are given emphasis among the respondents. The least in rank is "There is policy in addressing the behavior of students in the school based on trauma, violence, and mental health", with a weighted mean of 3.31 or Moderately Agree which means that policy on student behavior is implemented properly. The overall average weighted mean is 3.95 (SD=0.333) or Agree on the proper approaches to school system and discipline on educational leadership and practices in the area of disruptive behavior of students.

Hence, ethics in learning must be emphasized among students. This will lead them to a better leadership program in the school. They are provided necessary skills and engagement due to influential response and change through ethics and equity. It analyses the educational organization leadership in the influence of disruptive behavior among students. This must be implemented as a standard in learning. It emphasizes the necessity and essentials of ethics in school leadership where it needs to be recognized as an ethical imperative practice in the educational management leadership. It is a perspective and personal experiences of teachers to address the school system and discipline in the classroom behavior. It addresses complexities in the philosophical practice and principles in the school system and discipline for value inculcation in teaching and learning process. It ponders the ethical leadership that asserts the goals to define educational organization (Mallillin, & Caranguian, 2023, pp. 131-141).

Table 5

Proper Approaches to School System and Discipline on Educational Practice on Leadership in Terms of Improved Teaching Innovation

Indicators	WM	I	R
1. Improved teaching innovation increases the quality system and discipline in school.	4.13	A	4
2. It makes innovation effective in substantial distinction between teaching from the school system and discipline.	3.20	MA	6
3. It shows dominant assumptions in the school system discipline and effectiveness of innovation in teaching.	4.16	A	2.5
4. It adopts the procedures and given context methods of teaching and innovation.	3.71	A	5
5. It contains design and distinction implication of school system and discipline that emerges educational organization and perspectives.	4.16	A	2.5
6. It demonstrates teaching improved innovation for student engagement and conducive learning in a classroom setting diversity.	4.20	SA	1
Average Weighted Mean	3.93	A	
Standard Deviation	0.399		

It emphasizes in table 5 that rank 1 is "It demonstrates teaching improved innovation for student engagement and conducive learning in a classroom setting diversity", with a weighted mean of 4.20 or Strongly Agree which means that leadership teaching improved innovation plays an important role in the educational organization. Rank 2 is shared by the two indicators which are "It shows dominant assumption in the school system discipline and effectiveness of innovation in teaching", and "It contains design and distinction implication of school system and discipline that emerges educational organization and perspectives", with a weighted mean of 4.16 or Agree which means innovation of teaching in the school system and discipline is being stressed. Rank 3 is "Improved teaching innovation increases quality system and discipline in school", with a weighted mean of 4.13 or Agree which means that innovation function is for quality teaching to equip competency in learning. The least in rank is "It makes innovation an effective substantial distinction in teaching", with a weighted mean of 3.20 or Moderate Agree. This is always the goal of educational leadership and practices. The overall average weighted mean is 3.93 (SD=0.399) or Agree on the proper approaches to school system and discipline on educational leadership and practices in the area of innovation in teaching.

Therefore, innovation of teaching introduces pedagogical success inherent to educational practices in the school setting, pertinent facilities, and collaboration of learning. It offers better implication and innovative teaching and other similar contexts. It stimulates disputes in the improved innovation teaching. It influences innovation of teaching diversity techniques and strategies in the capacity of self-regulation school system and setting. Teaching strategies provide positive innovation, capacities, and discipline in school organization (Mallillin, 2022, pp. 99-121).

2. On the significant relationship on the proper approaches to school system and discipline in building a foundation success on practices of educational leadership

Table 6

Test of significant relationship on the proper approaches to school system and discipline in building a foundation of success on educational leadership and practices

Test of Variables	Computed z value	Interpretation	Decision
1. discipline in school	77.7517	significant	rejected
2. discipline inside the classroom	143.6955	significant	rejected
3. classroom management and learning	87.4047	significant	rejected
4. disruptive behavior of students	83.8340	significant	rejected
5. innovation in teaching	76.1994	significant	rejected
Two-tailed test, df of 150, at 0.05 level of significant, with critical z value of ± 1.96			

It reveals in the table 6 that all computed z values are higher than the critical z value of ± 1.96 , two-tailed test, df of 150, at 0.05 level of significance which shows significant and rejection of the hypothesis.

Therefore, it is safe to say that there is a significant relationship on the proper approaches to the school system and discipline in building a foundation of success in educational leadership as observed by the participants.

CONCLUSIONS

Discipline in school highlights the school system's capacity to be the priority for progress and improvement of educational organization where it measures the approach to school discipline and achievement of students.

Discipline in the classroom setting shows conditions in the learning process provided by the lecturers in giving proper motivation in the academic achievement of students where it provides a dimension apparent to the skills and achievement of students' learning process.

Classroom management and learning shows that learning is an out of base approach where the framework of the learning is being given and students are given enough time to explore the learning style and process where it emphasizes the school system and self-directed learning practices and challenges in the school setting.

Disruptive behavior of students shows emphasis in addressing the critical behavior of students where students are given orientation discipline inside the classroom to provide rich understanding principles inside the classroom and prepares students information in advanced utilization of learning appropriately to their behavior and services.

Innovation in teaching demonstrates students' engagement and conducive learning in a classroom setting diversity where it shows dominant assumptions in the school system discipline and effectiveness of innovation in teaching.

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